

these amino acids is : glutamic acid > leucine > phenylalanine > tryptophan > arginine > histidine > lysine. Glutamic acid being acidic amino acid, is eluted first, followed by the group of neutral amino acids (leucine, phenylalanine, tryptophan) and the group of basic amino acids (arginine, histidine, lysine). This agrees with the previously reported order for elution of amino acid using the Cu^{II} -form of the resin containing carboxylic acid or phosphonic acid groups⁶.

TABLE 1—YIELD OF AMINO ACIDS FROM TARAMIRA OILCAKE

Amino acid	Percentage Yield (%)	
	Proteinous residue	Raw oilcake
Arginine	9.0	5.94
Glutamic acid	16.5	10.89
Histidine	5.0	3.30
Leucine	2.8	1.84
Lysine	1.2	0.79
Phenylalanine	2.7	1.78
Tryptophan	2.3	1.51

The basic pattern of elution sequence of amino acids with Zn^{II} -form of the resin is the same as that with Cu^{II} -form. In the case of Fe^{III} , the order of the elution sequence is the same except that lysine is eluted before histidine. However, when Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} forms of resin were used in the column, the resin became black on adding the NH_4OH solution. The eluted solution gave a precipitate of metal showing the breaking of metal form of the resin. So Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} cannot be used for the separation.

In case of divalent metal ion, the elution volume is less with Zn^{II} -form of the resin than the Cu^{II} -form. This is in agreement with the fact that the Zn^{II} -amino acid complexes are less stable than the Cu^{II} complexes. The elution volumes in the case of Fe^{III} -form of resin are more than those of Zn^{II} -form while less than Cu^{II} -form of the resin.

The separation with Cu^{II} -form of the resin has been repeated thrice and it showed that the column chromatography technique can be used as a practical tool for the isolation of amino acids from taramira oilcake.

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A Comparative Study of the Efficacies of TLC/FID and Plate-TLC Techniques in the Separation of Phospholipids and Galactolipids

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THE separation of galactolipids from phospholipids, present in authentic standards as well as in cabbage extract, was compared by the use of Chromarod-Iatroscan system (including impregnations with boric acid and oxalic acid) and plate-tlc method (including double development). The results are reported herein.

Experimental

Silica gel Chromarods-S II (Iatron Labs, Japan) were used¹. The lipid standards used (Serdary Research Labs, Canada) were: phosphatidyl ethanolamine (PE), phosphatidylcholine (PC), monogalactosyldiglyceride (MGDG) and digalactosyl diglyceride (DGDG). All organic solvents were redistilled under nitrogen before use.

The air flow rate on the Iatroscan TH-10 Analyser (Iatron Labs, Japan) was 2000 ml min⁻¹, the hydrogen pressure 0.73 kg cm⁻² and the scan speed 2 mm s⁻¹. A Nissci Sangyo Instruments (Japan) model 50 strip chart recorder was used with attenuation of 10 mV and chart speed of 20 cm min⁻¹.

Plate tlc was executed on pre-coated plates (Adsorbosil-5 Prekotes, Applied Science Division, U.S.A.). These were predeveloped with ethyl acetate, activated at 110° for 45 min and then spotted (10 µl of the sample), air-dried, developed, air-dried and then dried at 110°, and finally sprayed with 2', 7'-dichlorofluorescein, concentrated H_2SO_4 , α -naphthol or exposed to iodine vapour.

The cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*) lipids were extracted as described by Peng². The extract was freed from the chlorophyll pigments by passing it through a SEP-PAK silica cartridge (Waters, U.S.A.) and eluting with chloroform³.

Results and Discussion

In the TLC/FID analysis several solvent systems were tried, viz. Me_2CO , $\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{MeOH}$, CHCl_3-

MeOH-H₂O, CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O-NH₄OH and CHCl₃-EtOAc-Me₂CO-MeOH-HOAc-H₂O for varying time periods (15-60 min). Out of these only the last two solvent systems, both with a 40 min development time, showed good separation. In the last named solvent system (60 : 12 : 15 : 16 : 3 : 3), PC and DGDG remained unresolved, although Mirayama and Morita⁴ reported that they had separated these under the same conditions. PC and DGDG could, however, be separated in the ammoniacal system (80 : 35 : 3 : 1), but in this system PE and MGDG coincided. Impregnation of the Chromarods either with oxalic acid (0.25 M in CH₃CN) or boric acid (1.2% in 1 : 1 aqueous EtOH) did not improve the resolution of the lipids.

In the plate tlc analysis, all the components of the mixture could be well separated using the acidic solvent system as stated above. In this system (visualisation by iodine vapour) the *R_f* values were : PC, 0.13 ; DGDG, 0.19 ; PE, 0.38 ; MGDG, 0.70. This was in fact better than the only other solvent system tried, viz. Me₂CO-MeC₆H₆-HOAc-H₂O (60 : 40 : 2 : 1), which was the best solvent system for galactolipids (*R_f* : MGDG, 0.11 ; DGDG, 0.05) but could not move the phospholipids. A similar observation had earlier been made by Goldschmidt⁵. Using double development technique, a separation of all the components could be achieved in Me₂CO-HOAc-H₂O (100 : 1 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH-HOAc-H₂O (25 : 15 : 4 : 2) on tlc plate, but the *R_f* values were closer, viz. PC, 0.26 ; DGDG, 0.30 ; PE, 0.57 and MGDG, 0.70. On the basis of our investigations, the application of both TLC and TLC/FID techniques using more than one solvent systems, seems to be a better approach for the separation of galactolipids from phospholipids.

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Ion-exchange Chromatographic Separation of Amino Acids on Impregnated Papers

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THE systematic applications of chromatographic methods made possible the quantitative separation, identification and estimation of amino acids in a

complex mixture with great speed, precision and sensitivity. These methods exploit differences in the solubility and acid-base behaviour of the different amino acids. The advantage of chromatography and ion-exchange can effectively be combined by the introduction of ion-exchange papers¹. The use of inorganic ion-exchangers as impregnating reagent, are preferred over their organic counterpart due to high selectivity and stability towards radiation and high temperature. The present communication describes the chromatographic behaviour and separation of few important amino acids on bismuth oxide impregnated paper using various aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed developing systems. Numerous physio-analytically important binary and ternary separations were achieved.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman no. 2 paper strips (18 × 3 cm) by ascending method. Chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade. The impregnation was performed as described in our earlier publication². The paper was conditioned for 15 min and the solvent was then allowed to ascend 15 cm in each case. The time required for the ascend of the aqueous and mixed developing solvent systems to a height of 15 cm was approximately 30-40 min.

A 0.2% solution of ninhydrin in n-butanol saturated with water was used as chromogenic agent for visualising the spots of amino acids on paper chromatograms. The *R_f* values were calculated as usual.

Chromatography : *R_f* values of the following 24 amino acids were calculated in 18 different aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed developing systems : glycine, DL-alanine, DL-2-amino-n-butyric acid, DL-serine, aspartic acid, L-glutamic acid, L-cysteine, L-cystine, DL-threonine, DL-methionine, DL-valine, L-leucine, DL-iso-leucine, DL-nor-leucine, L-lysine, L-arginine, L-ornithine, DL-β-phenylalanine, L-tyrosine, 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-DL-alanine, L-proline, L-hydroxyproline, L-histidine and DL-tryptophan. The various developing systems used were distilled water, 0.1 M aqueous sodium acetate and sodium potassium tartrate, methanol, ethanol, n-butanol, isobutanol, amyl alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, n-butanol saturated with water, n-butanol : acetic acid (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) and n-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 1 : 4, 5 : 2 : 3 and 5 : 4 : 1).

Separation : On the basis of appreciable difference in *R_f* values of amino acids, numerous binary and ternary separations were tried in different developing systems and some of the practically achieved physio-analytically important separations are as follow : (i) separation of L-glutamic acid (0.23) from aspartic acid (0.58) and L-arginine (0.11) from DL-methionine (0.57) in n-butanol saturated with water, (ii) separation of cystine (0.05) from cysteine (0.28), DL-serine (0.38) from DL-valine (0.66) and